

Abstract

The aim of this thesis is to explore and predict the optical, photovoltaic and transport characteristics of lead-free halide double perovskites by using first-principles methods for the construction of high efficiency photovoltaic cell and thermoelectric engine. Thus, we have studied the electronic structure, phonon spectrum, optical, photovoltaic properties and the derived transport properties are studied. The electronic, optical, power conversion efficiency and ZT are predicted for the few lead-free halide double perovskites. For this study, we have mainly applied density functional theory (DFT), semiclassical transport theory and SCAPS-1D simulation. This thesis is divided into six chapters. In first chapter, there is a introduction about photovoltaic and thermoelectric energy conversion. The properties related to the efficiency of photovoltaic cell, and figure of merit are described. Next, the reason behind the limitation in low efficiency, desire for high PCE, zT materials, desired material's features for good photovoltaic, thermoelectric material, criteria for large zT and conflicting relation among transport coefficients are mentioned. We have described few properties of lead-free halide double perovskites such as crystal structure and structural stability. Thereafter, we have described a brief background of DFT. In this chapter, we have discussed details about GGA-PBE exchange correlation and mBJ potential. Also, we have discussed about working principle of cubic package and phonon calculation. Finally, the details of working principle of SCAPS-1D simulation is discussed. This chapter starts with a discussion about the need for energy conversion materials and definition of photovoltaic materials. Also, we have discussed the significance of photovoltaic technology over non-renewable energy sources. Later, we have discussed about characteristics of solar cells. In addition to this, the PCE along with its relation to the material's properties is discussed. Next, we have defined the thermoelectric device and the efficiency of TEG, figure of merit, lead-free halide double perovskites materials and their properties. Thereafter, we have discussed about problem with thermoelectric parameters and approach to enhance figure of merit. Finally, we have discussed about structural, optoelectronic and thermoelectric properties of $A_2BB'X_6$. Moreover, the importance of $A_2BB'X_6$ as photovoltaic and thermoelectric materials are discussed. Chapter 2 provides a brief theory of the methods used in the thesis to study the electronic, phonon and transport properties of compounds. It starts with a description of DFT, then the Kohn-Sham equations and their self-consistent solution are briefly discussed. Next, the various XC functionals are discussed in subsection. The theory of semiclassical transport is given in next section. In the next section, we have discussed about phonon calculation. Then, the first-principles calculation techniques

of phonon properties are summarized. In the last, the details SCAPS-1D simulation and its working steps are mentioned. After this, the electronic and structural properties of $\text{Cs}_2\text{Tl}(\text{As}/\text{Sb})\text{I}_6$ are predicted. The phonon calculation shows they are thermodynamically stable. Also, the electronic properties shows that they are suitable for photovoltaic and TEG. Further studies revealed that they have outstanding optoelectronic properties required for green energy technology. Moreover, huge electrical conductivity, ultra-low thermal conductivity and large value of figure of merit (ZT) tells that they are TE materials. Thereafter, our motivation is predicting suitable photovoltaic absorber from lead-free halide double perovskite and modelling solar cell. For that, we have considered $\text{Cs}_2\text{GeSnCl}_6$ which shows good absorption. Furthermore, a solar cell having the structure of $\text{ITO}/\text{SnO}_2/\text{Cs}_2\text{GeSnCl}_6/\text{Au}$ was made which shows a maximum power conversion efficiency of 18.74%. Moreover, the higher ZT value of $\text{Cs}_2\text{GeSnBr}_6$ is coming from small k with large σ . Thus, $\text{Cs}_2\text{GeSnCl}_6$ is suitable for green energy technology. Next, we have studied the magnetic and spin-based thermoelectric properties of K_2WX_6 [$\text{X}=\text{Cl}, \text{Br}$]. The spin-polarized band structure along with density of states shows show the half-metallic nature of both compounds. Further, the calculated spin based optical properties shows that the down channel of both compounds is having higher order of absorption coefficient and low reflectivity which tells that we can use them for high efficiency solar cell by polarizing in down channel direction. The thermoelectric parameters are calculated to examine the suitability in spin based Seebeck effect. The high σ , S , PF , ZT and low thermal along the spin down channel demonstrated that we can use them for high efficiency thermoelectricity by polarizing in down channel direction. Finally, we have summarized the thesis with significant conclusion and future scope of my research area.